

On peer-mentoring for research productivity improvement

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“At a high level of knowledge, learning naturally has to be paired with practice.”

— In “Bird Village Economics”; *Wild Wise Weird* [1]

Abstract

This article proposes a peer-mentoring mechanism to support early-career researchers (ECRs), particularly those working under resource constraints. An efficient mechanism will require: a) Appropriate philosophical values; b) Well-functioning methodologies for conducting research; c) Rules for effective collaborative and communicative efforts using a shared platform, shared methodologies, data, and responsibilities; and d) Continual signs of progress of participatory peers measured in both productivity and quality. The mechanism is based on our real-world example of the SDAG Lab, the Interdisciplinary Social Research (ISR), the SM3D Portal, and the achievements of participants over the past 7 years. The SM3D Portal alone has enabled nearly 110 ECRs from 67 universities in 20 countries to successfully implement their research endeavors (including a dozen freshly minted Ph.D.). The peer-mentoring mechanism can open up collaborative research opportunities for early-career researchers (ECRs) across universities, enabling them to start their active publishing careers more productively and joyfully. We trust (based on our data) that many will see the process as less stressful and less painful, which likely enables them to pursue a long-term academic pursuit.

Keywords: peer-mentoring mechanism; early-career researchers (ECRs); knowledge production; innovative capacity; Granular Interaction Thinking Theory (GITT)

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Guiding Philosophical Principles for Research Practice

Interdisciplinary research has become a global trend, aiming to generate knowledge, foster innovation, and develop solutions to pressing global issues such as climate change, environmental sustainability, public health, artificial intelligence, food security, sustainable urbanization, and global peace governance [2, 3]. In this context, I (VQH) founded the SDAG Lab and Interdisciplinary Social Research (ISR) Center on August 1, 2017, under what is now Phenikaa University (then operating under the name Thanh Tay University).

The early years of the SDAG Lab and ISR “startup,” if it may be called so, were marked by uncertainty and considerable risk. Funding was limited. The workload was overwhelming. The team consisted of only four members, with just two serving full-time.

At that time, the practice of conducting and publishing international research was still unfamiliar to most faculty and researchers in Vietnam, apart from a few well-established research centers, typically in the fields of natural sciences and technology.

In the face of these initial challenges, we proposed three core philosophies to ensure ISR's survival and development: cost-effectiveness, a spirit of transparency, and a proactive attitude [4-6]. A cost-effective mindset and proactive attitude help researchers thrive under resource constraints, while a transparency-oriented spirit can reduce the cost of conducting science and strengthen its self-correcting mechanism [7].

These core philosophies served as the foundation for the following operational principles that have guided our research programs:

- (i) First, the team needed tools that would reduce the financial costs associated with conducting research.
- (ii) Second, we promoted a culture of early data and code sharing, along with preliminary results, to facilitate collaboration among researchers across different locations and time zones. Over time, this practice also contributes to lowering research costs.
- (iii) Third, we emphasized data processing skills to enhance efficiency, thereby creating a "time surplus" compared to periods before the use of effective tools. This surplus could then be allocated for more in-depth conceptual thinking and rigorous interpretation of the findings.
- (iv) Fourth, we did not treat peer review and editorial decisions as the sole gold standards. Instead, we focused on thorough investment in logic verification, theoretical grounding, and the coherence of argumentation as the core academic values.

These principles enabled us to achieve major goals despite severely constrained research conditions. Among our most notable achievements is the successful development of a theoretical and methodological ecosystem—starting with the Mindsponge Theory (MT) [8], followed by the bayesvl package and Bayesian Mindsponge Framework (bayesvl/BMF) methodology [9, 10], and most recently, the Granular Interaction Thinking Theory (GITT) [11].

As of June 11, 2025, the Center has documented 244 scholarly outputs (including journal articles, books, dissertations, conference proceedings, and lecture materials) applying MT, bayesvl/BMF, and GITT in a substantial way. This figure represents a 45.24% increase

since the previous record on January 21, 2024, and a 90.63% increase compared to July 9, 2023. These works were authored or co-authored by 543 researchers from 345 institutions in 53 countries, of which 387 researchers (71.27%) are from developing or emerging economies [12]. Table 1 presents the cumulative counts of recorded publications and completed manuscripts that have utilized bayesvl/BMF in research, along with the corresponding cumulative numbers of contributing authors, institutions, and countries.

Table 1: Cumulative number of recorded publications and completed manuscripts using bayesvl/BMF

	Cumulative number of works	Cumulative number of authors	Cumulative number of institutions	Cumulative number of countries
Publications	76	143	181	18
Completed Manuscripts	113	162	196	20

Given the demonstrated effectiveness of these principles—and in light of the ongoing pressures faced by the scientific community, particularly since the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic and the global decline in research funding—we recognized the opportunity to share and apply these insights on a broader scale. As a result, we launched the SM3D Portal, a community coaching platform, to support training in social science research methodology for Early Career Researchers (ECRs) and those working under resource constraints: <https://mindsponge.info/about> [13].

Community Coaching on the SM3D Portal: A Real-World Application

The SM3D Portal is a community-based scientific training platform developed based on three core scientific philosophies upheld by the ISR: transparency, cost-effectiveness, and proactive engagement [4-6]. The platform operates within the SM3D knowledge management ecosystem, which is short for Serendipity–Mindsponge–3D [14]. The SM3D Portal initiative was launched with three primary goals:

1. To promote knowledge exchange and facilitate global collaboration grounded in openness, transparency, equity, and creativity;

2. To create opportunities for researchers, especially early-career scholars and those with limited resources, to participate in joint research projects using the BMF analytical framework;
3. To provide an enabling environment where members can discuss intriguing scientific findings, co-produce scholarly outputs, and enhance essential research skills through theoretical, technical, and editorial support from the ISR team.

Since its official launch on June 22, 2022, the SM3D community has initiated over 100 collaborative research projects, training nearly 110 researchers from 67 institutions across 20 countries. Notably, 85.2% of participants are researchers from developing countries. The scholarly outputs generated through this training process have been published in various reputable journals, including *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications* (Nature Portfolio), *Thinking Skills and Creativity* (Elsevier), *Environmental Conservation* (Cambridge University Press), *Current Issues in Tourism* (Taylor & Francis), *International Journal of Human-Computer Interaction* (Taylor & Francis), *Marine Policy* (Elsevier), *Sustainability* (MDPI), among others.

Through their active engagement in SM3D projects, many members have not only developed their capacity for independent research but have also made significant career advancements.

For instance, Dr. Ruining, one of the first young scholars to join the community while serving as a postdoctoral researcher at China University of Political Science and Law, has since been appointed as a full Research Professor at the Institute of Higher Education, Beijing University of Technology. Similarly, Dr. Wulan from Widya Mandala Catholic University Surabaya, who joined the Portal in 2023, was recently promoted to Professor following her substantial research contributions to her institution.

Through the SM3D community's academic collaborations, Dr. Wulan has swiftly established a broad international research network spanning Vietnam, China, Australia, and several African countries. Notably, she is currently invited to guide BMF-based research methodologies for doctoral students at the University of Pretoria (South Africa), University of Nairobi (Kenya), and Chinhoyi University of Technology (Zimbabwe). With her commitment to learning and determination to overcome challenges, Dr. Wulan has made remarkable strides in her academic career—just under two years ago, she was still a young researcher exploring ways to develop her skills and scholarly mindset. In

recognition of her outstanding contributions, she was recently nominated as Outstanding Faculty Member of 2024 by Widya Mandala Catholic University Surabaya.

After three years of implementing SM3D scientific coaching, we have come to realize that the SM3D Portal holds great potential to evolve into a platform for peer-mentoring in interdisciplinary research. In the next section, we will introduce the proposed peer-mentoring mechanism, its underlying rationale, and the theoretical foundation based on GITT, a theory founded on worldviews of quantum mechanics [15, 16], Shannon's Information Theory [17], and Mindsponge Theory [8].

Toward a Collaborative Peer-Mentoring Mechanism

According to Granular Interaction Thinking Theory (GITT) [11], knowledge production is a dynamic, multi-state process that requires contributions from multiple individuals. Since the future is probabilistically shaped by—but not deterministically fixed by—the past, it is crucial to maximize the probability that useful knowledge (or scientific output) can be transmitted from one state (State 1) to another (State 2). In this view, research collaboration represents a process in which knowledge from various sources (i.e., various scholars) in a prior state (State 1) is combined to create new knowledge in a subsequent state (State 2). This process is dynamic, and its effectiveness depends heavily on the interactions among participants.

Interdisciplinary collaboration increases the diversity of informational inputs—such as knowledge, skills, and perspectives—being integrated into the knowledge production process. This, in turn, raises the probability of producing valuable scientific findings and discoveries. However, the more collaborators involved and the more distinct informational inputs they bring, the higher the entropy of the system becomes. Therefore, to maintain effectiveness, the quality of interactions among participants is critical in reducing this entropy.

To better understand this process, we can refer to Shannon's informational entropy formula [17]:

$$H(X) = - \sum_{i=1}^n P(x_i) \log_2 P(x_i)$$

Here, $H(X)$ represents the entropy (i.e., missing information or uncertainty) of a random variable X with possible outcomes $\{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\}$ and corresponding probabilities

$\{P(x_1), P(x_2), \dots, P(x_n)\}$. In this context, n indicates the number of distinct pieces of information (e.g., knowledge, skills, perspectives) involved in the interdisciplinary knowledge production process. The higher the value of n appears, the higher the entropy and the more energy and time will be needed to produce structured, low-entropy knowledge.

It is important to note that peer-mentoring mechanisms differ fundamentally from hierarchical mentoring structures, where designated mentors guide and instruct trainees (i.e., $P(x_{Mentor}) > P(x_{Mentee})$) and create a low-entropy state of knowledge production. In contrast, given the nature of interdisciplinary collaborations, each participant may possess unique strengths from which others can learn, making mutual exchange essential for progress. As a result, peer mentoring should treat all participants as having equal probability to influence the flow of knowledge production ($P(x_1) \approx P(x_2) \approx \dots \approx P(x_n)$). In other words, any participant can be simultaneously a mentor and a mentee in specific areas of knowledge, which increases the whole knowledge production process.

To reduce this entropy, quality interactions—through discussion, critique, coordination, and mutual validation—must occur to reach consensus. In this process, the first two principles of scientific collaboration (mentioned in Section 1), namely (i) openness and transparency and (ii) cost-effectiveness, play a foundational role. Achieving these principles require well-functioning methodologies for conducting research and rules for effective collaborative and communicative efforts, using a shared platform, shared methodologies, data, and responsibilities. The bayesvl software, the Bayesian Mindsponge Framework (BMF), and the SM3D Portal, which were specifically designed to facilitate these goals, can serve achieving these targets well. When principles (i) and (ii) are ensured, participants have more time and cognitive capacity to focus on principle (iii): investing time effectively in thinking and collaborative discussion of research findings.

Moreover, participants are not merely passive providers of information—they also serve as filtering systems, evaluating, classifying, prioritizing, and discarding low-utility information. This filtering mechanism enhances the likelihood of uncovering meaningful insights, thereby increasing the chances of generating valuable scientific knowledge. In essence, it is a method of entropy reduction—optimizing the probability distribution of information usage by excluding irrelevant or misleading data from the production process. To make this process effective, the (iv) principle—intellectual humility and interdisciplinary openness—is essential. It encourages participants to avoid disciplinary

biases and to prioritize careful scrutiny of logic, theoretical grounding, and argument coherence as core scientific values.

Building on the peer-mentoring mechanism, we propose that universities can form small research groups of 3–5 members to reduce the cost of conducting research amid declining scientific funding while preserving the effectiveness of epistemic production. These groups would function in an interdisciplinary, peer-to-peer format, with each member contributing distinct strengths and perspectives. This structure promotes knowledge diversity and fosters mutual learning dynamics. Progress would be assessed in phases, aligned with key milestones in the research cycle, to ensure both accountability and adaptability.

Furthermore, universities can serve as central hubs by linking their internal groups with external research teams, thereby expanding collaborative networks. By adopting this peer-mentoring model, universities not only reinforce their role as research incubators but also contribute to the development of a distributed, self-sustaining knowledge ecosystem—one in which small, peer-led teams function as foundational units of innovation, interaction, and capacity building.

***Note:** We are open and committed to welcoming and supporting institutions, research groups, and researchers who wish to explore, engage with, and collaborate in applying the mentor-mentoring mechanism. For inquiries, please contact Dr. Minh-Hoang Nguyen at hoang.nguyenminh@phenikaa-uni.edu.vn or nmhhg8@gmail.com.

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